

JANE FINCH COMMUNITY RESEARCH PARTNERSHIP

NOVEMBER 29 2016, SYMPOSIUM REPORT

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Note:

The Jane Finch Community Research Partnership planning group was made up of Abena Offeh-Gyimah, Lorna Schwartzentruber, Maura Matesic, Andrea Kosavic, Krista Jensen, and Natalie Coulter.

The symposium notes were provided by Zivi Richard (MSW Candidate, York University). The photographer was Errol Young.

Executive Summary

The Jane and Finch Community Research Partnership (JFCRP) held a symposium that brought together community residents, organizations, and York University academics on Tuesday November 29, 2016. The gathering addressed challenges in accessing research about or conducted in the Jane and Finch community as well as the ongoing challenging relationship between Jane-Finch and York University around research ethics. The need for a community ethics process is necessary to guide and inform how research is conducted in the community. The day was informed by a JFCRP event held June 2016 and a previous symposium, *Connect the Dots*, hosted on December 11, 2013.

The day started with presentations on community examples of research from two community groups and one community organization: *The Black Creek Food Justice Network*, *JFAAP*, & *PEACH*. Their reports highlighted resident-led projects that not only engaged residents with issues that impact their everyday lives but also the participation of residents in informing solutions that are beneficial to the community at large.

This was followed with a closer look at the Indigenous Research Protocol at York University by Deborah McGregor and the need for research ethics principles built on effective university-community relationship. Also, the York Ethics Review Board gave a presentation on the York ethics process with Allison Collins-Mrakas highlighting opportunities for Jane-Finch residents to participate on York University ethics board.

In the afternoon the York Knowledge Mobilization Unit and Library gave presentations on open repositories and knowledge mobilization, which then led to brainstorming sessions on the various ways of accessing research. A key outcome of this symposium was to mobilize community members and create working groups that will focus on identifying and developing various aspects necessary for the formation of a community resource center/online repository as well as community ethics principles that inform research relationships between York University and the community. These questions were starting points for the various working groups:

Community Ethics Principles

1. What are the underlying principles for ethics?
2. How can we apply these principles to the York-Jane and Finch relationship?
3. How would these principles inform and frame an approach to community ethics?

Community Resource Centre/Archive and/or Knowledge Mobilization Efforts

1. What are the necessary community guiding principles for a resource centre?
2. What might a resource centre/repository look like?
3. Who would deposit material and/or how will access to certain materials be mediated?

Background & Context

The Jane and Finch Community Research Partnership (JFCRP) is a group that came together as a response to the lack of access to research done in/about Jane-Finch. JFCRP ventured to better understand how residents want to access research done on the community as well as participate collaboratively on any future research conducted on the community. JFCRP organized an event in June that brought community residents and York University researchers to share their perspectives and thoughts to two primary questions: what research is being done in the community? How do you want to access the research of the community?

The presenters at this event discussed tools to collect and disseminate research. Residents highlighted the troubling research relationship between York University and the Jane-Finch community, specifically, around research outcomes that benefitted the community in meaningful and sustainable ways. Small group conversations identified themes of power, oppression, inequitable access to resources among others for on-going consideration and a need to take the conversation further meant a first step necessitates acknowledging and addressing the history between the Jane-Finch and York University.

The history between York University and the Jane Finch community is a complex one. To begin, there have been historical accounts of inequitable relationships created by the power imbalances between the academic institution and the community, which has left longstanding tensions. The relationship between the two has not always been mutually beneficial, and often the community is over-researched, over-analyzed, and objectified for the gain of the academic institutions and individual researchers.

One of the prominent examples of this historical relationship has been demonstrated in the inequitable research encounters, between York University and the community. There have been documented occurrences of “parachuting,” which is an extractive process whereby researchers treat community members as “data points” or “subjects” (Connecting the Dots 2013). The communities’ marginalized status has led to many professors and students working from deficit perspectives and operating from saviour complex standpoints, which has resulted in many researchers conducting research projects that aim to save the community from its many documented ills. In turn, this has resulted in many Jane Finch residents often complaining of being “over-researched” and patronized as the community is treated as a research laboratory by York (and other institutions), and the effect is ultimately having their voices misrepresented. Residents are often asked objectifying questions based on preconceived notions of the community -- something community activists refer to as the “petting zoo effect” whereby residents are treated as though they are part of a museum exhibition (Connecting the Dots 2013). The unequal relationship develops as York, and its student researchers gain academic prestige, community members rarely get access to the data, and are often left feeling objectified.

As such in the winter of 2013, the York U-TD Community Engagement Centre (CEC) hosted a group of community residents, organizers, community organizations from Jane-Finch along with faculty and staff of York University who came together for a one-day symposium

which “sought to address both the historical and the contemporary oppressive structures, practices and relationships that have existed and continue to exist between York University and the Jane-Finch community” (Connecting the Dot 2013).¹ From this event, a report was released which outlined key concerns of the community as well as action items, future objectives and descriptions of best practices and recommendations for more healthy mutually beneficial community-University relationships.

Community Research Experiences Mural

The below images are taken from the mural paper posted entitled “Community Research Experiences.” Attendees, from York, community and residents alike, were encouraged to record insights or produce an image that spoke to the topics and issues being discussed.

¹ *Connect the Dots* runs training sessions for York University students doing their placement at community organizations in Jane Finch. The training covers topics like the history of Jane Finch and the historical relationship between Jane Finch and York University. The focus is on unpacking power, privilege, oppression and racial profiling; de-bunking and challenging media perceptions, stereotypes and stigma about the community; the importance of cultural sensitivity and culturally relevant grounding and context, and the difference between research and extraction.

Welcome & Opening

Facilitators: Sam Teclé and Abena Offeh-Gyimah

Sam Teclé is a PhD candidate in the Sociology Department at York University. His areas of focus include Black Cultural Studies, Sociology of Education and Community Based research. He is a Jane and Finch resident and teacher and community worker in the City of Toronto for over 15 years.

Abena Kwatema Offeh-Gyimah is a PhD student at McMaster University in the School of Social Work, resident of Jane and Finch, and a previous intern (2014) and also coordinator (2015-2016) of the youth internship farming program at Black Creek Community Farm (BCCF). In addition, she is a member of the Jane Finch Community Research Partnership (JFCRP). Her graduate research studies the history of Black farming settlements in Canada and the role of land in the current struggles for food justice.

The distinction that comes from the popular euphemism “town and gown” stems from long histories of separation between universities and communities. Often, this separation is meant to refer to often unequal relationships academia sometimes has with its nearby communities. The longstanding relationship between York University and the Jane and Finch community fits into this unfortunate historical context - as there exists a long history of researchers from academia producing narratives of Jane and Finch, its residents and community in general, from a deficit perspective. This very long standing production of harmful stories about Jane-Finch has been exacerbated by outside researchers receiving funding and resources to come into the community to “extract” information, experiences and human resources, without re-investing or building trusting relationships with the community. This reality has left many from the community with deep wounds and traumatic memories. Often, it is the case that marginalized communities do not have the resources or capacity to sustain meaningful conversations about ethics and repositories in order to build more positive relationships. We – that is to say the university, its researchers, community members and residents - must come together to rethink how to implement measures for more positive future research relationships that strive for more collaborative projects as well as means and measures by which to protect our community from future harm.

Framing the Day: Community-Led Research

The morning began intentionally by highlighting examples of community based research where the relationships, partnerships and results of the projects were beneficial to all organizations and community partners involved.

Welcome to PEACH: Community Hosts for the Day

Talisha Ramsaroop

Talisha Ramsaroop is a long time Jane Finch community worker, developer and resident. Talisha just completed her Masters in sociology from York University which was focused on community murals in the Jane finch community. In 2015 Talisha was awarded the Sir Lincoln Alexander Community Award as well as the 100th North York Citation and the Urban Hero Award. She has also been featured in Canadian Living's Top 40 Change Makers and recently did a Tedx talk about debunking stereotypes.

The day began with a welcome from and brief introduction to the community organization in which the event was being held, Promoting Education and Community Health (PEACH).

Located within the Jane and Finch community, PEACH has over 25 years of experience working at the grassroots level to advance innovative programs that directly impact the community in deep ways. Their focus is to promote education and community health in the Jane-Finch community for youth and their families. PEACH provides a web of front-line youth services and experiential educational programming. Youth come to PEACH programming for: Ontario Secondary School credit recovery delivered through the School Away from Schools program; to learn about music theory, sound engineering and music recording through the Rhyme N' Reason program, utilize the studio during drop in, and learn about STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) skills with the Innovation Hub. PEACH also works on advocacy and is currently advocating for an assets based approach in Jane Finch through the 40 Assets Model and a pre-charge diversion program specific to community needs.

Black Creek Food Justice Network

Rosalyn Endlich, Rosie Mensah & Butterfly Gopaul

Rosalyn Endlich has been involved with the Black Creek Food Justice Network since 2014, most recently as a co-coordinator. Rosalyn is a horticultural apprentice and works at Downsview Park in Toronto. Additionally, she recently completed a master's degree in Environmental Studies at York University, studying urban agriculture and food justice.

Rosie Mensah, resident of the Jane and Finch community, is a Master of Public Health student at the University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health. Rosie is a Past Coordinator and current member of the Black Creek Food Justice Network and is currently pursuing Registered Dietitian credentialing with a keen interest in food justice, food security and health equity.

Sabrina “Butterfly” Gopaul works with a number of grassroots groups in the Jane and Finch area and across the city of Toronto. She’s been working with JFAAP for over 5 years responding to the social determinants of health in the community of Jane and Finch/Black Creek. Butterfly is an advocate for issues related to children/youth, women, access to education/employment, policing/community safety, social justice using the arts and affordable housing. Butterfly voices passionate viewpoints about her lived experiences and her vision for a stronger, more organized and mobilized Jane and Finch community and City of Toronto.

The Black Creek Food Justice Network (BCFJN) is a resident led group concerned with the challenge and issues related to food injustice in the Black Creek Community. Through the City of Toronto’s Access and Equity grant, the BCFJN was able to undertake a Food Justice project within the larger Jane-Finch community. The project engaged community residents to share their experiences around food through community consultations and the “Humans of Black Creek Project.” BCFJN also conducted a food frequency radio show, and among other important projects, the September Day of Action took partners and residents to the street to raise awareness on access to healthy and nutritional food as a human right. The BCFJN supports organizations that do justice work around food, such as Justicia 4 Migrant Workers (website down, but refer to resource <https://harvestingfreedom.org/>).

The findings of the project were brought together in a report titled, *Fighting for food Justice in the Black Community* that highlighted residents' lived experiences around their access to food. The key themes looked at how food intersects with migration, policing, capitalism, mental health, and etc. A

list of demands came out to address immediate work that can be done to support food justice throughout the city, but more so, with a focus on Jane-Finch. The demands call attention to improving growing spaces, making food accessible, and putting a stop to the ongoing criminalization in the community. The report comes with an ethical use guideline that encourages the report to be shared, however, when it is used, especially by organizations, to honor the process from which it came and to also consider ways in which the report will be used to support the demands for food justice.

The Network meets every fourth Monday, at 6pm at the Black Creek Community Farm (4929 Jane St, North York, ON M3N 2K8). This report is accessible both in the form of a hard copy and online which can be accessed here: http://tfpc.to/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/FullReport_small.pdf

PEACH

Jane Finch Youth Asset Mapping Project – Ayo Milap Aigbedion

In the summer of 2015 Ayo Aigbedion was a youth researcher working for PEACH on a youth-led community asset mapping project on youth friendly spaces in Jane Finch. Ayo is a recent high school graduate who is looking to start a career in the social services sector as a social worker. Ayo is looking to apply to either Humber College or York University in the fall.

In 2015, with support from the Canada Summer Jobs Grant, Stephanie Mazerolle, Program Manager from PEACH, assembled a research team of four youth members from the community to conduct an asset mapping project of Jane and Finch. The asset map was based on how youth used community space. A primary goal of the project was to survey youth and capture their perspectives on the strengths, needs and available resources in the community. Briefly, the Research Design consisted of four youth leading the asset mapping, receiving researching training on interpreting data and conducting the analysis of findings. The youth research team was able to collect 140 completed surveys, compiling an impressive amount of data and conducted final analysis. Participants who completed the short survey were between the ages of 16-29 and completed a questionnaire focusing on what they needed and wanted to see in their community.

Once the data was accumulated, the youth mapped community space based on two criteria: where youth were going and frequented and secondly on where youth felt safe. Using Google Maps and GIS programming, youth mapped the space onto a digital map of Jane and Finch offering a refreshing and dynamic way to present research findings. A logical next step to the project and yet another intriguing way of presenting research findings, the youth research team proposed developing a Jane and Finch app. Yet, with limited resources and grant money running out this remains a challenge. Briefly, some important needs were identified, youth who were surveyed marked accessing mental health services and obtaining access to an up-to-date directory of all available services to youth as persisting issues. Presenting this research highlighted the important, potential and potency of community-based and community-led research, insight as to how to meaningfully engage youth in community-based research at all points of the research process, achieved by hiring them, training them and building their capacity as researchers - which resulted in a project led by and for youth producing research on youth in Jane and Finch. Comments from those assembled reflected on the exciting possibilities this project opened up for “deep mapping,” which entails researching and inputting historical knowledge behind the mapped dots. For future consideration, one participant from the audience suggested that the HackFest at York’s Library could be a possible partnership to move forward with developing an app.

Jane Finch Action Against Poverty (JFAAP)

Butterfly Gopaul

JFAAP is a grassroots community group with an 8 year organizing history in the community. The group was founded in 2008, following a rally in response to the International Day for the Eradication of Poverty. JFAAP has had a number of connections to York University and acknowledge that there are some really good individual and informal relationships with professors, student bodies, activists and community residents. However, they challenged York as an institution to think more sustainably in its relationship with the community. Often those relationships are lost when people change positions and transition into other work, leaving the community to start from scratch despite a long history of being part of the same community.

One of the initiatives that grew out of JFAAP was *Connect the Dots* - a conference (as previously referenced), and a training program (2013 and 2014) with the York-TD Community Engagement Centre for students who were doing placements or research in the Jane Finch Community. *Connect the Dots* was a process to create space for conversations about resident's feelings of research exploitation and the continuation of narratives which sensationalized issues in the community. It also voiced the disparity of resources between the University and the community, and that while researchers gained large research grants in the name of the community, there was often nothing left behind, and few efforts to leverage its power and resources on behalf of the community.

The *Connect The Dots* Report can be found here: <http://cec.info.yorku.ca/connect-the-dots/>

Butterfly closed the JFAAP presentation recognizing the many other partnerships, relationships, reports or initiatives between York University and the Jane Finch community:

- Success Beyond Limits
 - Ongoing, started off as summer program of grade 8 students would come to York to get an advanced credit.
- Chronicles of the Outspoken
 - Community artists, Westview, art education and helping youth discovering their creative capabilities.
- Generation Change
 - TDSB with York, youth ambassadors for Pan Am games.
- ACTT
 - York University School of Social Work with community organization conducted interviews and research on Jane-Finch youth.
 - Resulted in NOISE
- Westview Alliance at York to connect and create support for students
- The ACE program
- Readers 2 Leaders
- York-TD Community Engagement Centre
- Black Creek Community Farm

Considering Ethics

Ethics at York University

Alison Collins-Mrakas, M.Sc., LLM

Alison Collins-Mrakas is the Senior Manager and Policy Advisor, Office of Research Ethics at York University, which is a position she has held for over 13 years. Alison has been teaching for the past three years at Seneca College a research ethics course titled "Ethics and Regulatory Requirements in Clinical Trials". Alison is a former Municipal Councillor for the Town of Aurora.

This presentation centered on how the Research Ethics Office and team provide assistance to faculty, staff and students conducting research with humans, animals and biological agents. Rather than thinking of her team and function as that of the “ethics police,” the Office of Research Ethics ensure that York’s Research Community remain compliant to approved research processes and adhere to changing regulations and ethics review processes. The function of Mrakas and her team is to provide the pathway for research projects to move forward with the assurance of regulatory and ethical compliance. Rather than write research protocols, the Office of Research Ethics reviews and approves all research projects done under the purview of York University, which remain compliant with tri-council policy statements.

Mrakas’ presentation provided engaging and substantive responses to the need for ethics processes governing research projects. She cited historical examples of the Belmont Report, which comes out of the horrendous terror of 1930s Tuskegee Trials, out of which a national commission on research was the result. Shortly thereafter ethics became a staple underpinning all research activities. For Mrakas, a key takeaway from this historical example was that ethics is not just a piece of paper, but a process. Ethics ensures researchers remember that participants are important and vital to research, but also that they have a responsibility to protect their rights, no matter how laudable an end might be. Ethics Review is necessary to ensure research is conducted responsibly, to protect research subjects and to protect the researchers. The core principles of research ethics review is respect for persons – autonomous and right to say I don’t want to participate in research, have the right to say half way through to withdraw at any point without penalty. Secondly, a concern for the welfare of participants, clearly detailing risks and benefits. Ethics review ensures that time is spent asking the question “What are you asking people to do? What benefits will they get from this project?” Thirdly, justice is a core principle of ethics review, which asks why are you recruiting people? What are the inclusion and exclusion criteria? Is the group an easy or captive group? Mrakas also noted that there exists an over representation of certain people in research and that clinical trials most often consist of orphans, institutionalized people, military personnel and people in prisons.

Mrakas also noted that ethics review is required for research that is funded or not, and any for research conducted by faculty, staff and students. Also, under the purview of the review include such items as the focus group design, survey and questionnaires - noting that even family and informal conversations, if under the guise of research, would need to be consensual. Relatedly, data security is an often underappreciated aspect of ethics processes in research. Researchers

must think of the full life cycle of data: why are you collecting it? Consideration must be taken for the number of different requirements of personal identifiers, and the implications of a breach. What are the risks to your participants in the case of a breach of data? These are all vital components for sound ethical research to take place. As is apparent, qualitative research projects are the most difficult to review as ethics guidelines are based on the assumptions that you're doing research about what you claim to be, a fairly linear approach. The problem is that community based or participatory research do not fit nicely into boxes - the flexibility is in process rather than form.

Indigenous Protocols for Community Research

Dr. Deborah McGregor

Deborah McGregor joined the Osgoode Hall Law School faculty in 2015 as a cross-appointee with York University's Faculty of Environmental Studies. Professor McGregor's research has focused on Indigenous knowledge systems and their various applications in diverse contexts including water and environmental governance, environmental justice, forest policy and management, and sustainable development. Her research has been published in a variety of national and international journals and she has delivered numerous public and academic presentations relating to Indigenous knowledge systems, governance and sustainability.

Dr. McGregor's presentation outlined indigenous ethical principles that guide the research relationship between the university and indigenous communities. For universities to effectively conduct community research, they must first develop and build relationships with communities and avoid labeling marginalized communities continuously as "vulnerable" and "high risk".

Researchers and communities have their own values and perspectives derived from their cultures and histories, which influences ways of collecting and generating knowledge and meaning. The ongoing discussions about researching indigenous people in their communities have led to the development of an Indigenous ethical framework for working with research institution. These guiding principles are more intentional and humanizing than Universities' standards.

The Royal Commission on Aboriginal Peoples states that appropriate respect must be given to cultures, languages, knowledge and values of Aboriginal peoples. The standards used by Aboriginal peoples are needed to legitimize the knowledge collected and used. Working with indigenous communities requires an acknowledgement of how the history of knowledge production has always placed them on the margins. For example, in academic context, for a long time Elders were not (and in many places *are not*) recognized as experts. This contributed to the ongoing harm often done without providing opportunities to correct misinformation or to challenge ethnocentric and racist interpretations. The existing bodies of research, which normally provide a reference point for new research, must be open to reassessment.

When studying a body of knowledge there is a need for an accountability process, and guided by ethical principles. Universities must be very critical of their position of power and why they are conducting research in specific communities. Several indigenous communities have developed their own protocols that can be useful for others.

For example, the National Aboriginal Health Organization and Aboriginal research in First Nation communities in the Manitoulin area have developed protocols that emphasize transparency, demonstrate benefits to the community, and recognize that traditional people and elders are the knowledge holders.

All research conducted in indigenous communities goes back in a format that is meaningful.

The seven principles teachings of the Creator for Anishinaabe peoples that inform research ethics are: humility, bravery, honesty, wisdom, truth, respect, and love.

Access to Research

Open Repositories

Andrea Kosavic

Andrea Kosavic is interim Associate University Librarian for Digital Services at York U. She has worked in the area of digitization and digital collections since the late 1990s. At York, her support of digital projects has focused on scholarly communications initiatives including the York Digital Journals publishing support program and the YorkSpace institutional repository. Her research interests include: scholarly communication, publishing, copyright, gift economies, social capital, and interoperability. Andrea is currently a member of the Public Knowledge Project Members Committee, the Public Knowledge Project Education Group, and the Ontario Council of University Libraries Scholars Portal Committee. She served on the Synergies Canada National Technical Committee from (2007-2012), and as an Ontario Library Information Technology Association Councillor (2010-2012). She was also co-founder of the Ontario Council of University Libraries Publishing/Hosting Community.

Andrea discussed open access and community values around repositories. Open access repositories carry specific values of: equal unrestricted access to research materials; copyrights remain with authors; rejection of inequality of research based on economic class and institutional affiliation; diminish publisher exploitation of public funds; transparent, open technical infrastructure (shared back to the community) and alternative measures of impact (ways research evaluated, clique behaviour, journals that are considered to be high impact, institutional affiliation will be rejected solely by affiliation of author.)

Open access movement and advocacy seek alternative ways of making research available without cost. Repository platforms are designed in specific ways that enable for the sharing of dissemination capabilities, discoverable and findability of scholarship. The benefits of repositories are, but not limited to: used only for formal research outputs, they become community spaces; and communities can create and manage their own collections. However, maintaining a repository means the need to make sure they are kept for the public good; preserving infrastructure; creating exposure and dissemination of what is posted.

Andrea expanded her presentation by drawing on what a community would want out of a repository. A community repository would be framed in community values and ethics, mindful of long tradition of harm to the community, should control and prevent exposure to harmful

research, showcase research created by residents themselves, include reviews of works, included research must pass ethics, help Residents interpret research outputs, include capability for community to curate content and add context; and promote interest in seeing community based research in progress.

A website is not a repository. There exist particular tools such as Sherpa/Romeo that can inform whether an article can be deposited in an institutional repository. Some questions to consider around a community repository will revolve around “gatekeeper”, thinking more so around the lines of a community license and/or community approval. Also, considering how credit will be appropriately given to the community as well as community expectations that govern how a repository work is used. Some ongoing questions are: Will a repository serve the community? How will community ethics and values be represented? (Ethical use license) How will potential for harm be minimized? Who will manage what gets included?

Knowledge Mobilization

Krista Jensen

Krista Jensen is a Knowledge Mobilization Officer at York University. She holds a Master of Information Studies degree from the University of Toronto, and has experience working in not-for-profit special libraries, as well as research services, focusing on information management, research dissemination and the use of technology and social media tools in research collaborations. Krista is also a PhD student in the Faculty of Education at York University and is investigating knowledge sharing in online environments.

Knowledge Mobilization is ensuring that scholarship is connected to the larger community and is meaningfully translated and relevant to community partners and others. Yorks KM Unit provides services to faculty, staff, students, and community partners and recognizes that both the community and academia have knowledge to share.

Some of the ways they assist are by connecting researchers with the community, helping the community access research, offering networking events, providing clear language research summaries, build capacity and use of social media as a tool for knowledge mobilization, helping outline knowledge mobilization strategies for grant proposals, and help developing social media strategies. They can help in all areas of knowledge mobilization planning, including honing in on the main message, identifying the audience, and assessing impact of the project. Clarifying roles and responsibilities of project participants is part of the process, including acknowledgement of power and structural violence. MOU’s can address these responsibilities as well as outline expectations regarding access to and use of the research, and conflict resolution.

Krista gave examples of mobilizing research. This included:

Products (Blog, Case study, E-newsletter, Educational material, Fact sheet,FAQ, Handbook, Journal article, Magazine article, Newspaper article, Podcast, Powerpoint presentation, Press

release, Promotional material, Reference list, Report, Research summary, Success story, Toolkit, Video, Webinar, Website content, Wiki);

Events: (annual meetings, awards ceremony, conference, debate, forum, interactive workshop, lunch and learn, media event, panel, presentation);

Social Media Tools: (Blogging, Twitter, Facebook, Pinterest, Youtube, Instagram, Slideshare);

She closed her presentation highlighting some recent innovative Knowledge Mobilization projects, such as:

- Infographics: Active Living Research - Active Kids Learn Better
- Research Summaries: Taking academic research and training students to translate it into grade 8-10 language.
- Posters
- Vimeo.com
- Video overlay with dance, and quotes from research.

Next Steps: Working Groups

Towards the end of the daylong conference, the attendees focused on what action steps could be taken to move forward the work of more sustainable and less inequitable research relationships between the community and York. Based on expertise and interest, it was agreed that two working groups would be formed, one on *Repositories* and the other on *Ethics*. This decision came out of two large group discussions towards the end of the day that focused on the forming of a repository and on how to have more community input on the ethics process at York University for any research projects based in (and on) the Jane and Finch community.

The guiding questions for the discussion on *Repositories* were:

- a) What might be community guiding principles for a resource centre?
- b) What might a resource centre/repository look like?
- c) Would a deposit and/or access of certain materials be mediated?

Some initial suggestions and points of consideration from the conference for the *Repositories* Working Group:

- Initial statement that the space must exist due to long history of trauma in community of being over researched
- Intention of re-evaluating and being critical of what knowledge is deemed “important” or “expert”

- All involvement of experiential education (placements) training and research must be approved and ongoing through the resource centre
- Community Resource Centre is the body through which York University must be accountable:
 - York University is not the gate keeper to resident knowledge and research
 - York University is to commit to their ideas of social justice in real tangible ways with the Jane-Finch community
 - York University must invest in relationships with Jane-Finch community
- Community Capacity building mandate
- Community License: Community has the intellectual property and that all knowledge belongs to the community
- Onus is on researchers to ask community to use data
- All resources and services to be free

Services/Activities of the Resource Centre:

- Resources agglomeration of projects, reports, initiatives etc. (Academic, Community and Grey literature) on Jane-Finch to be available in Digital & physical formats
- Collection of literature reviews, tool kits and grey literature resources
- Document produced on Jane-Finch research needs:
 - What are active projects currently happening,
 - List of what we need to know
- Having a physical space
 - Art exhibits, stage for performances for expressive styles, art space, music, recording studio
- Space for disseminating/capacity building on research/work/findings regularly (symposiums, conferences, workshops etc)
- Graduate students engagement & involvement
- Provide support to residents who are in undergrad/grad school
- Community members be on committees for grad studies approval of thesis & dissertations
- Production and delivery of an ethical framework process, and record an “ethics of care” for relationship of York with the community, then shapes how we do resource center development
- Reinvigorate and delivery of curriculum like Connect the Dots.
- Must have institutional support – (Has to be financially supported and institutional commitment, partners in resources, community control not jeopardized. Engaging government, city)

And for the discussion on *Ethics* the guiding questions, were as follows:

Community Ethics Principles

- a) What are the underlying principles for ethics?
- b) How can we apply these principles to the York-Jane and Finch relationship?

c) How would these principles inform and frame an approach to community ethics?

The initial suggestions and points of consideration for the *Ethics* Working Group are below:

- Need for transparency and resident engagement in the tri-council Vice-President of Research review committee
- Bridging need for York to make reconciliation of research
- If someone experiences harm during a research process: breach of ethics. What has occurred and reconciliation has to be part of the ethics process
- Committee for collaborative research – York faculty, students, administrative offices, and other issues. Not everything is ethical violation, faster system to deal with issues in a systemic and collaborative way. Lacking concrete steps to formation of this process
- Subject in an ethics protocol, issues are about how community is portrayed and research being done. Flag or identify for Jane-Finch to have documentation to get sense of volume of research being done from York Ethics board and having it presented in the community
- Avenues should be explored to have community representation on the York ethics board, i.e. Jane-Finch person to review research that is based on this community
- Evaluation with community partnerships existing and ongoing
- Making relationship links with ministries and other government partners

The Jane and Finch Community Research Partnership Committee (JFCRP) will take leadership on forming the working groups. Towards the end of March, it is the hope that another half day meeting will take place to reconvene all participants to update the collective of the action steps.

